

UNIVERSIDAD
DE GRANADA

Hybridization of FDTD with Shielded Multiconductor Transmission Lines and ngspice junctions (EMI Analyses and Predictions - 3)

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Motivation

Take-home message: we want to include in a 3D FDTD full-wave solver the capacity to treat arbitrary wiring networks with arbitrary connections

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Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) is a widely used method to discretize Maxwell's equations in time and space and solve CEM problems

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \nabla \times \mathbf{H}$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{H}}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{\mu_0} \nabla \times \mathbf{E}$$

How to treat **sub-cell** structures?

but Courant (stability condition):

$$\Delta t \leq \Delta x / c \cdot \sqrt{3} \text{ and } N_{\text{steps}} = t / \Delta t$$

$$\Downarrow \Delta x \quad \longrightarrow \quad \Downarrow \Delta t \quad \Uparrow N_{\text{steps}}$$

Holland thin-wire formalism

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\mu \frac{\partial \mathbf{H}}{\partial t}$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \epsilon \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} + \sigma \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{J}_s$$

$$\uparrow \mathbf{I} \quad \downarrow \mathbf{E}$$

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial t} = -c^2 \frac{\partial Q}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{L} \langle E_z \rangle$$

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial I}{\partial z}$$

✗ TW can be extended to multiwires, but not to arbitrary bundles (nested shielded transmission lines)

✗ Connections between wires limited to RLC components: not arbitrary & scale poorly with complexity

Proposal: full-wave + MTL + ngspice

Full-wave domain (3D): planewave incidence, E/H update, field probes, boundaries, bulk bodies (PEC or other materials)

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Multiconductor Transmission Line (MTL) domain (2D + 1D):

2D: computation of p.u.l. parameters (dedicated solver)

1D: I/V update of single wires, shielded multiconductor transmission lines and bundles; I/V probes, shield transfer impedance, connectors (line-structure connection)

full-wave - MTL integration: formulation

Field domain
MTL domain

Maxwell's equations: field propagation and interaction with currents

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \times \mathbf{E} &= -\mu \frac{\partial \mathbf{H}}{\partial t} \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{H} &= \varepsilon \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} + \sigma \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{J}_s\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\partial_z \{\mathbf{V}\} &= -[\mathbf{L}] \partial_t \{\mathbf{I}\} - [\mathbf{R}] \{\mathbf{I}\} + [\mathbf{Z}] * \{\mathbf{I}\} + \{\mathbf{E}_T\} \\ \partial_z \{\mathbf{I}\} &= -[\mathbf{C}] \partial_t \{\mathbf{V}\} - [\mathbf{G}] \{\mathbf{V}\} + [\mathbf{Y}] * \{\mathbf{V}\}\end{aligned}$$

Telegraphist equations: (V,I) update in **bundle** and interaction with external field

- $\{\mathbf{V}\}, \{\mathbf{I}\}$: vectors of voltages and currents ($n \times 1$)
- $\{\mathbf{E}_T\}$: external field (outermost conductor) ($n \times 1$)
- $[\mathbf{L}], [\mathbf{C}], [\mathbf{R}], [\mathbf{G}]$: p.u.l matrices ($n \times n$)
- $[\mathbf{Z}], [\mathbf{Y}]$: shield transfer impedance and admittance ($n \times n$)

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$$[\mathbf{Z}] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & Z_{T,12} & Z_{T,13} & 0 & 0 \\ Z_{T,12} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ Z_{T,13} & 0 & 0 & Z_{T,34} & 0 \\ Z_{T,35} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Z_{T,43} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Z_{T,53} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

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ngspice domain (0D): circuit solver to advance voltage at cable ends and interconnections; sources, passive and electronic components

MTL - ngspice integration

FDTD discretization

Circuit analog of the extreme of the transmission line: simulated by ngspice, V passed back to MTL. Z_1 is the ngspice circuit of the connection:

- lumped components
- sources
- electronic components

Experimental validation

TEM cell. Test planewave on:

- bare wire
- shielded wire (with Z_T)

Wire panel. Transmission lines:

- ended in electronic components
- with & without crosstalk

TEM cell

- Away from the source, $20 \times 20 \times 20 \text{ cm}^3$ volume where wave is \sim TEM
- Place test object at the center of this volume
- Field intensity (needed in simulation) measured at the same position

[Starprobe FL7006 field probe](#)

Bare wire

- Wire length ≈ 7 cm
- Field amplitude ≈ 1.85 V/m (measured w/ field probe)
- $f \approx 550$ MHz (best S/N ratio)

Uncertainties (lower limit):

- simulation: field level (± 0.8 dB), wire length (± 1 cell = 0.5cm)
- measurement: oscilloscope precision

Shielded wire

RG 58/U coaxial:

- $r_w = 0.8128 \text{ mm}$ (20AWG)
- $r_{sh} = 1.5 \text{ mm}$
- $\epsilon_{diel} = 2.0-2.1$
- $Z_T = 0.01 \Omega \cdot \text{m}^{-1} + j\omega \cdot 1 \text{ nH} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$

Field amplitude = 43 V/m (amplified)

$f \approx 550 \text{ MHz}$

Ended in 50Ω

Uncertainties (lower limit):

- simulation: field level ($\pm 0.8 \text{ dB}$), wire length ($\pm 1 \text{ cell} = 0.5 \text{ cm}$), Z_T ($\pm 25\%$)
- measurement: oscilloscope precision

Wire panel

Works as one- and two-conductor TL

Used to test:

- line terminations with electronic components:
 - zener diode
 - operational amplifier TL701CP (*Texas Instruments*)

ngpsice terminations: zener diode

- Zener diode ($V_B = 3.9$ V)
- Excitation: 5 V, 50 kHz sinusoidal signal
- Clipping at ~ 0.7 V (typical of Si diodes) and 3.9 V

ngpsice terminations: op-amp

- Wire panel with op-amp at line end (10x inverter amplifier, $V_{in} = \pm 15V$)
- Test no saturation ($V_{src} = 0.2V$) and saturation regime ($V_{src} = 2V$)

Crosstalk in components

- Excitation on a wire, same op-amp at the end of the other wire
- Test with sinusoidal and square pulse
- $f = 1 \text{ MHz}$, $V = 20 \text{ V}$: need high frequency and amplitude to have a measurable crosstalk

sine pulse

square pulse

Conclusions

- Hybridization of 3D-FDTD with MTL and ngspice: networks of shielded bundles, with arbitrary interconnections, in a full-wave solver.
- ngspice interconnections: allow for electronic components, straightforward simulation of dispersive elements in time domain
- Experimental validation of simulations covering main new features.
- All tools integrated in *openSemba*, a full-wave open-source FDTD solver
 - You can find it at <https://github.com/OpenSEMBA>
 - You are welcome to try it! More users, better software

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Backup

Iterative solution

Fields

$$\mathbf{H}^{n+1/2} = \mathbf{H}^{n-1/2} - (\Delta t/\mu)\nabla \times \mathbf{E}^n$$

$$\mathbf{E}^{n+1} = \frac{\varepsilon - \sigma\Delta t/2}{\varepsilon + \sigma\Delta t/2} \mathbf{E}^n + \frac{2}{\varepsilon + \sigma\Delta t/2} \left(\nabla \times \mathbf{H}^{n+1/2} - \mathbf{J}_s^{n+1/2} \right)$$

Transmission line (interior)

$$\mathbf{V}_k^{n+1} = \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} \mathbf{C} + \frac{\Delta z}{2} \mathbf{G} \right)^{-1} \left[\left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} \mathbf{C} - \frac{\Delta z}{2} \mathbf{G} \right) \cdot \mathbf{V}_k^n - (\mathbf{I}_k^{n+1/2} - \mathbf{I}_{k-1}^{n+1/2}) \right]$$

$$\mathbf{I}_k^{n+3/2} = \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} \mathbf{L} + \frac{\Delta z}{2} \mathbf{R} \right)^{-1} \left[\left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} \mathbf{L} - \frac{\Delta z}{2} \mathbf{R} \right) \cdot \mathbf{I}_k^{n+1/2} - (\mathbf{V}_{k+1}^{n+1} - \mathbf{V}_{k+1}^n) \right]$$

Transmission line (extremes) (circuit equivalent)

$$I_S^{n+1/2} = I_1^{n+1/2} + C \frac{\Delta z}{2} \partial_t V_1^{n+1/2} + G \frac{\Delta z}{2} V_1^{n+1/2}$$

$$I_L^{n+1/2} = I_N^{n+1/2} - C \frac{\Delta z}{2} \partial_t V_{N+1}^{n+1/2} - G \frac{\Delta z}{2} V_{N+1}^{n+1/2}$$

Transmission line (extremes) (needs I)

$$\mathbf{V}_1^{n+1} = \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} \mathbf{C} + \frac{\Delta z}{2} \mathbf{G} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} \mathbf{C} - \frac{\Delta z}{2} \mathbf{G} \right) \mathbf{V}_1^n - 2 \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} \mathbf{C} + \frac{\Delta z}{2} \mathbf{G} \right) \mathbf{I}_1^{n+1/2} + \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} \mathbf{C} + \frac{\Delta z}{2} \mathbf{G} \right)^{-1} [\mathbf{I}_S^{n+1} + \mathbf{I}_S^n]$$

$$\mathbf{V}_{NDZ+1}^{n+1} = \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} \mathbf{C} + \frac{\Delta z}{2} \mathbf{G} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} \mathbf{C} - \frac{\Delta z}{2} \mathbf{G} \right) \mathbf{V}_{NDZ+1}^n + 2 \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} \mathbf{C} + \frac{\Delta z}{2} \mathbf{G} \right) \mathbf{I}_{NDZ+1}^{n+1/2} - \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} \mathbf{C} + \frac{\Delta z}{2} \mathbf{G} \right)^{-1} [\mathbf{I}_L^{n+1} + \mathbf{I}_L^n]$$

Bundle

full-wave - MTL integration: p.u.l matrices

$$[L] = \begin{bmatrix} [L]_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & [L]_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & [L]_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{matrix} [L]_1 = L_{\text{in-cell}} & [L]_2 = [L]_{2 \times 2} \\ [L]_3 = [L]_{2 \times 2} \end{matrix}$$

$$[C] = \begin{bmatrix} [C]_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & [C]_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & [C]_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{matrix} [C]_1 = C_{\text{in-cell}} & [C]_2 = [C]_{2 \times 2} \\ [C]_3 = [C]_{2 \times 2} \end{matrix}$$

$$[Z] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & Z_{T,12} & Z_{T,13} & 0 & 0 \\ Z_{T,12} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ Z_{T,13} & 0 & 0 & Z_{T,34} & 0 \\ Z_{T,35} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Z_{T,43} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Z_{T,53} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$[G] = (\sigma/\epsilon) [C]$$

$$[R] = [R]_{5 \times 5}$$

$[L]$, $[C]$ pul matrices ($n \times n$):

- full-wave domain: in-cell
- MTL domain: ii, ij , to reference conductor (2,3 \rightarrow 1), (4,5 \rightarrow 3)

$[Z]$ matrix ($n \times n$):

- input, provided by manufacturer or characterized by dedicated measurements
- current on wire \rightarrow voltage on shielded/shield

Complexity/Electrical size

Image sourced from: <https://help.altair.com/feko/>

TEM cell antenna factors

- Problem with excitation:
 - ideally lightning-like pulse in **time**
 - experimentally: if pulse has frequency spectrum \rightarrow pulse in generator \neq pulse in cell (antenna-factors: $V_{\text{cell}}(\omega) = V_{\text{gen}} \cdot AF(\omega)$)
 - simulation: needs $E(t)$ in cell
- To ensure comparison under the same excitation:
 - sinusoidal function
 - monochromatic $\rightarrow \omega$ in generator = ω in cell
 - measure amplitude inside with field probe

Unshielded multiwires

- Case in [A multiwire formalism for the FDTD method](#) (J. P. Bérenger, 2002)
- Two-wire multiconductor, without shielding, excited by external field
- No experimental validations so far, visit pending to UPC labs

Dielectric coating (sim)

$$\begin{aligned}d_1 &= 3.18 \text{ mm} \\d_2 &= 3.18 \text{ mm} \\ \epsilon_r &= 3.2\end{aligned}$$

$$V(t) = \exp(-g^2(t - t_{max})^2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}g &= 2.5 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ s}^{-1} \\t_{max} &= 8.6 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ s}\end{aligned}$$

- Monopole antenna over ground plane (1)
- Image equivalent, antenna twice as long, no plane (2)
- Current measured at the base of (1), the center of (2)

Dielectric coating (exp)

- Experimentally, hard to measure
- Dielectric, not thick enough, not ϵ enough
- Delay in measurements, within resolution

